

Readiness for Online Learning: A Study of Perception among Culture and Arts Students

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Abstract: This study focuses on the online learning readiness of culture and arts students. The aim of this study was to analyze the readiness of culture and arts students in terms of confidence and importance category. The research tool which is the “Student Readiness for Online Learning (SROL) Instrument” developed by Florence Martin, Brandy Stamper, and Claudia Flowers was used in this study. The result showed that students have a very high level of readiness towards online learning in terms of importance and high level of readiness in terms of confidence. This suggest that despite the sudden shift of the learning platform, students are still ready to learn through the utilization of the internet and digital tools.

Keywords: Confidence, Culture and arts, Importance, Online learning, Perception, Readiness.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the past few years, the world experienced a lot of changes brought about by the emergence of information and communication technology. Several aspects of people’s lives were affected by these changes and it undeniably manifested itself in the field of education (Herguner et al., 2020). Interestingly, different educational institutions formulated a new learning style in response to the rise of technological innovations. This new learning style is what they call online learning (Herguner et al., 2020). Online learning expresses a very different learning environment where students’ learnings are not only dependent on the resources found in the classroom but they can now learn through different online resources.

Since students are now very exposed to online learning with the use of technology, it is important to determine whether they have the ability and the competence to adjust in this type of learning. For students to have a successful online learning experience, they should possess online readiness (Artino, 2009; Kruger-Rose and Waters, 2013; Mercado, 2008). Readiness for online learning is defined by Borotis and Poulymenakou (2004) as “being mentally and physically ready for online learning experience and actions.” It is further elaborated as the competency to use certain e-resources such as the internet (Choucri et al., 2003). The readiness of students should be consistently analyzed since it affects their academic achievement (Mosa, Mahrin, & Ibrahim, 2016; yilmaz, 2017). It is therefore important to examine online learning with respect to students’ readiness.

Different studies about online preparedness were investigated not only among students from International Universities but also among teachers. In the study conducted by Ates-Cobanoglu and Cobanoglu (2021), they investigated the online readiness of student teachers in Turkey according to different variables. It was found out that internet access and ICT competency are among the factors that affect the readiness of student teachers. Previous studies were also conducted concerning the readiness of music teachers for online learning (Kibici & Sarikaya, 2021). However, it was found out that male music teachers, music teachers with low professional experience and teachers working in private schools were found to have a high level of preparedness on online learning.

Research literature also investigated the effect of online learning attitudes of sports sciences students on their online learning readiness (Herguner et al., 2021). The findings showed that online attitude had a significant effect on their online

learning readiness. Naji et al. (2020) also examined the online learning readiness of engineering students in Qatar. The study implied that PBL students were more prepared than non-PBL students in terms of online learning. On the other hand, mathematics students' readiness towards online learning was also examined. This is in the study conducted by Suryanti, Sutaji, and Iswanti (2021) which found out that ICT competency had a high importance in math students' preparedness towards online learning.

However, the aforementioned studies conducted in determining preparedness towards online learning were centered upon teachers, student teachers, and students from different fields of specialization such as mathematics and engineering, but still there is no study conducted having Culture and Arts students as their respondents. Moreover, there were still no investigations conducted with regards to students' online learning readiness in the Philippine context.

Hence, this study aimed to supplement the gap that the existing studies failed to consider. This study explored the Culture and Arts students' level of preparedness towards online learning in the Philippine context.

Research Questions

This study sought to investigate the following research questions:

1. What is the level of online learning readiness of Culture and Arts students in terms of confidence category?
2. What is the level of online learning readiness of Culture and Arts students in terms of importance category?

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Online learning

Online learning, which was largely recognized in the field of education (Pillay, Irving and Tones, 2007), is defined as a learning process that allows students to access many learning resources at the same time even though they are far from the traditional learning environment (Caliskan, 2002). According to Stein, Shepherd and Harris (2011), online learning promotes the use of technology as it was deemed to be important in the teaching and learning process. According to the same author, it is an important variable that aims to enhance the pedagogical subjects related to digital literacy. Online learning in the Philippines has been widely used during the pandemic (Pesidas et al., 2022)

In the concept of Isaac et al. (2019), online learning was expressed as *blended learning*, *e-learning*, and *distance learning*. This was further defined as an operational learning that happened in a synchronous and asynchronous setting (Batmang et., 2021) through the use of the internet and different online platforms (Herguner et al., 2021). This type of learning enables students and teachers to have a convenient and efficient time using technology that would allow them to have a better learning experience (Bernard et al., 2004).

However, Omrod (2016) posited four key principles that are necessary in online learning. These are competence, enthusiasm, self-determination, and communication. These principles would help not only students but also teachers in having a successful online learning experience.

In the twenty-first century, students place a high value on technology and place their trust in it. They spend a significant amount of time on digital technology, whether it's surfing, searching, viewing internet videos, or even carrying out academic obligations and activities in the classroom. It is common to hear from kids that they are unable to distinguish between their daily lives and digital devices (Grant, 2011). Because of this, if we ignore online learning, we risk closing a valuable door on the future of teaching and learning in the twenty-first century, thus, this study aim and focus on online learning as a fundamental tools in continuing the education of the students despite circumstances and challenges, online learning will become the new normal in the future especially for the next generation and to fill in the gap in the research literature is the purpose of this study, in which online learning in the context of Culture and arts students as respondent is nowhere to be found in the literature.

Readiness towards Online Learning

Readiness is considered to be an important variable in the teaching and learning process (Bloom, 1995). In the educational environment, readiness towards online learning centered on the enhancement of strategies, instructions, and technological skills which were embedded in socio-cultural activities (Cheon et al., 2021; Dabbagh, 2007). Borotis and Poulymenakou (2004) mentioned that online readiness is being prepared intellectually and physically in different online environments. While Choucri et al. (2003) defined it as having the competency to use materials associated with e-resources such as the internet.

In other studies, they considered online learning readiness in other aspects. Warner et al. (1998) defined this in three ways: (1) a learning modality that students favored to the face to face education, (2) the ability of students in operating and manipulating different technologically aided learning materials, and (3) the capability to be part of independent learning.

Literature said that there are advantages in online learning (Bates, 2005), and that the use of intelligence and technology made learning more accessible. (Broadbent & Poon, 2015; Celen et al., 2011; Lim & Richardson, 2016). In this sense, students must have to be ready in online learning in order for them to achieve the benefits that this entails (Alsancak-Sirakaya & Yurdugul, 2016; Chung et al., 2020) which is called Online learning Readiness. Readiness towards online learning was claimed to be associated with students' participation (Demir-Kaymak & Horzum, 2013) and online learning success (Demir-Kaymak & Horzum, 2013; Galy, Downey & Johnson, 2011; Horzum et al., 2015).

Research studies concerning online learning readiness were investigated having 306 university students from Law Faculty and the departments of English Language Teaching and Physical and Sports coming from different state universities (Herguner et al., 2020). The results showed that the online learning attitude of learners has a positive effect on their online learning readiness. On the other hand, high Internet access determines a high readiness towards online learning among preservice teachers in Turkey (Ates-Cobanoglu and Cobanoglu, 2021). Moreover, in the study of Yeşilyurt (2021), he examined the readiness of high school students towards online learning and found out that they were high in computer literacy and computer based self-confidence. Engineering students in Qatar were also the respondents of the study conducted by Naji et al., (2020) to find out their initial readiness to transition to emergency online learning.

Teachers were also deemed to have an immense responsibility in providing online learning in the educational environment. This is the reason why Music teachers were also examined in terms of their online learning readiness in the investigation conducted by Kibici and Sarıkaya (2021). 203 teachers in secondary and high school were the respondents of the study, and results showed that male music teachers, music teachers with low professional experience and teachers working in private schools were found to have a high level of preparedness on online learning. In addition, Ergene and Türk Kurtça (2020) investigated the relationship between the online learning readiness and academic procrastination behaviors of the pre-service mathematics teachers. Results showed that there is a low-level significant relationship between the academic procrastination tendency and online learning readiness.

Based on the aforementioned related studies, the researcher therefore conclude that readiness for online learning in the context of culture and arts students as respondent is still lacking and through this research, the gap in the literature will be fill and knowledge will be further nourish in the context of readiness of students in particular the culture and arts student in the Philippines. Therefore this study is important and necessary as we are already in the 21st century.

3. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research study design that was used is descriptive quantitative design. It is utilized to determine the students' level of readiness towards online learning. The year level of the respondents was one of the information gathered to determine the statistical difference among Bachelor of Culture and Arts students in their readiness towards online learning when grouped according to year level.

Research Tools

The instrument used in this study was adopted from the instrument developed by Martin called the Student Readiness instrument for Online Learning (SROL). The questionnaire is answerable with a four-point Likert scale consisting of 20 statement items that are organized into four subscales with 5 items each: (1) online student attributes, (2) time management, (3) communication, and (4) technical. Respondents rated each item twice, once for the confidence in their readiness for online learning and once for the importance of online readiness competencies, which provided 40 responses and eight subscales.

Pilot Testing

The questionnaire was divided into 4 parts. The first part was the letter of consent and confidentiality. Second was the demographic profile in which participants were asked to provide their year level. Third, were the survey questions about the confidence of the students' readiness for online learning which has 20 items. The last part was the 20 item questions

about the importance of online readiness competencies. Majority of the respondents were third year students (43.3%), followed by fourth year students (23.3%), next were the second year students (20%), and the least numbered respondents were the first year students (13.3%).

Reliability of the Instrument

The questionnaire that was used for pilot testing was tested for reliability. The overall reliability of the questionnaire was determined as 'excellent' with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.919. In terms of students' confidence in their readiness for online learning, the reliability of each subscale was examined: Online student attributes has a reliability score of 0.720, time management- 0.787, communication- 0.727, and technical- 0.491. On the other hand, the importance of online readiness competencies was also examined in terms of its reliability scores of the four subscales: online student attributes has a reliability score of 0.932, time management- 0.854, communication- 0.895, and technical- 0.821. However, the study of Suryanti et al. (2021) which was the inspiration of this study did not indicate the reliability scores of the instrument as well as its subscales, the reason why there was no comparison made to compare its reliability scores to this present study.

Coding Procedure

The questionnaires used in the study were coded using SPSS to allow analyses on the data. The year level of the respondents was coded as 1 for first year, 2 for second year, 3 for third year, and 4 for fourth year. The responses provided in the SROL with regards to the respondents' confidence in their readiness for online learning were coded in the questionnaire as follows: 1 for Very Confident, 2 for Somewhat Confident, 3 for Neither Confident or Unconfident, 4 for Somewhat Unconfident, and 5 for Very Unconfident. Similarly, the importance of online readiness competencies were also coded as: 1 for Very important, 2 for somewhat important, 3 for neither important or unimportant, 4 for somewhat unimportant, and 5 for very unimportant.

Data Gathering Procedure

The research tools after validation was set for pilot testing which were utilized via google form. Due to the restrictions brought by the pandemic, online platforms such as messenger, were used in order to provide the link to the students. There were a total of 30 students who responded in due time for the analysis of data.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondents' Level of Readiness based on Confidence Category

To answer the research question number 1, the data were coded and analyzed to determine the level of students' readiness towards online learning in Table 1.0. To answer research question number 2, the data were analyzed and coded in Table 2.0 in which it presented the four subscales of the instrument: online student attribute, time management, communication, and technical competence, in the category of confidence. Each of the items displayed the frequencies and equivalent percentages, and the mean (M) and interpretation (Interp.) - 1.0 to 1.79 (Very Low Level of Readiness [VLLR]), 1.8 to 2.59 (Low Level of Readiness [LLR]), 2.6 to 3.39 (Neither High or Low Readiness [NHLR]), 3.4 to 4.19 (High Level of Readiness [HLR]), and 4.2 to 5.0 (Very High Level of Readiness [VHLR]). The overall mean and interpretation were also presented below each of the subscales.

Table 1.0 Descriptive Analysis of Level of Readiness in Online Learning based on Confidence

#	Very Unconfident	Somewhat Unconfident	Neither Confident or Unconfident	Somewhat Confident	Very Confident	Mean	Interp.
1	Set goals with deadlines.						
	0 (0%)	6 (7.1)	21 (24.7)	38 (44.7)	20 (23.5)	3.8471	HLR
2	Be self-disciplined with studies.						
	0 (0%)	2 (2.4)	25 (29.4)	38 (44.7)	20 (23.5)	3.8941	HLR
3	Learn from a variety of formats (lectures, videos, podcasts, and online discussion/conferencing).						
	0 (0%)	4 (4.7)	19 (22.4)	37 (43.5)	25 (29.4)	3.9765	HLR

4	Be capable of following instructions in various formats (written, video, audio, etc.).						4.1059	HLR
	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	20 (23.5)	36 (42.4)	29 (34.1)			
5	Utilize additional resources to answer course-related questions (course content, assignments, etc.).						3.9529	HLR
	0 (0%)	2 (2.4)	23 (27.1)	37 (43.5)	23 (27.1)			
Overall						3.9553	HLR	
6	Devote hours per week regularly for the online class.						3.8000	HLR
	0 (0%)	1 (1.2)	37 (43.5)	25 (29.4)	22 (25.9)			
7	Stay on task and avoid distractions while studying.						3.5529	HLR
	1 (1.2)	11 (12.9)	23 (27.1)	40 (47.1)	10 (11.8)			
8	Utilize course schedule for due dates.						3.6941	HLR
	3 (3.5)	6 (7.1)	23 (27.1)	35 (41.2)	18 (21.2)			
9	Complete course activities/assignments on time.						3.8941	HLR
	1 (1.2)	6 (7.1)	19 (22.4)	34 (40.0)	25 (29.4)			
10	Meeting multiple deadlines for course activities						3.7471	HLR
	1 (1.2)	8 (9.4)	29 (34.1)	29 (34.1)	18 (21.2)			
Overall						3.1776	HLR	
11	Use asynchronous technologies (discussion boards, email, etc.).						3.7412	HLR
	3 (3.5)	3 (3.5)	27 (31.8)	32 (37.6)	20 (23.5)			
12	Use synchronous technologies (Webex, Collaborate, Adobe Connect, Zoom, etc.) to communicate.						3.9765	HLR
	1 (1.2)	3 (3.5)	17 (20.0)	40 (47.1)	24 (28.2)			
13	Ask the instructor for help via email, discussion board, or chat.						3.8235	HLR
	0 (0%)	7 (8.2)	22 (25.9)	35 (41.2)	21 (24.7)			
14	Ask classmates for support (accessing the course, clarification on a topic).						4.1176	HLR
	1 (1.2)	4 (4.7)	18 (21.2)	23 (27.1)	39 (45.9)			
15	Discuss feedback received (assignments, quizzes, discussion, etc.) with the instructor.						3.6588	HLR
	0 (0%)	8 (9.4)	31 (36.5)	28 (32.9)	18 (21.2)			
Overall						3.8635	HLR	
16	Complete basic computer operations (e.g., creating and editing documents, managing files, and folders).						3.9412	HLR
	4 (4.7)	4 (4.7)	15 (17.6)	32 (37.6)	30 (35.3)			
17	Navigate through the course in the Learning Management System (e.g., Moodle, Canvas, Blackboard, etc.)						3.9647	HLR
	0 (0%)	8 (9.4)	32 (37.6)	30 (35.3)	15 (17.6)			
18	Participate in course activities (discussions, quizzes, and assignments. synchronous sessions).						3.9647	HLR
	0 (0%)	8 (9.4)	14 (16.5)	36 (42.4)	27 (31.8)			
19	Access the online grade book for feedback on performance.						3.5294	HLR
	0 (0%)	7 (8.2)	40 (47.1)	24 (28.2)	14 (16.5)			
20	Access online help desk/tech support for assistance.						3.6353	HLR
	0 (0%)	9 (10.6)	26 (30.6)	37 (43.5)	13 (15.3)			
Overall						3.7365	HLR	

The data presented in Table 1.0 were interpreted as High Level of Readiness utilizing the four subscales in the confidence category. Results show that the component with the least average mean value was the Time Management with a mean score of 3.1776, compared to the three components: online student attribute (3.9553), communication (3.8635), and technical competence (3.7365). Findings in the research of Handang (2022) also show a similar least mean value in the component of time management compared to the three components.

On the other hand, the item that gained the highest mean score of 4.1176 was the item 14. It could be concluded that students gained more confidence through the support of their classmates. The result was also similar to the findings in the paper of Handang (2022) explaining that location and culture were among the factors why support system was important in online learning setting. He justified that the nature of the respondents, being Filipinos, as communicative and friendly in nature were the reasons why supporting one another in an online setting mean a lot to them to gain confidence.

It was believed that most of the Culture and Arts students have a high level of readiness towards online learning because of the fact that online classes and online tutorials were one of the new ways to learn.

Respondents' Level of Readiness based on Importance Category

The data presented in Table 2.0 were code and analyzed to know the level of students' readiness in their perception on the importance of online learning. Table 2.0 presented the four subscales of this competency: online student attribute, time management, communication, and technical competence. Each of the items displayed the frequencies and equivalent percentages, and the mean (M) and interpretation (Interp.) - 1.0 to 1.79 (Very Low Level of Readiness [VLLR]), 1.8 to 2.59 (Low Level of Readiness [LLR]), 2.6 to 3.39 (Neither High or Low Readiness [NHLR]), 3.4 to 4.19 (High Level of Readiness [HLR]), and 4.2 to 5.0 (Very High Level of Readiness [VHLR]). The overall mean and interpretation were also presented below each of the subscales.

Table 2.0 Descriptive Analysis of Level of Readiness in Online Learning based on Importance

#	Not Important At All	Unimportant	Neither Important or Unimportant	Somewhat Important	Very Important	Mean	Interp.
1	Set goals with deadlines.						
	0 (0%)	1 (1.2)	10 (11.8)	22 (25.9)	52 (61.2)	4.4706	VHLR
2	Be self-disciplined with studies.						
	0 (0%)	4 (4.7)	12 (14.1)	16 (18.8)	53 (62.4)	4.3882	VHLR
3	Learn from a variety of formats (lectures, videos, podcasts, and online discussion/conferencing).						
	0 (0%)	1 (1.2)	9 (10.6)	22 (25.9)	53 (62.4)	4.4941	VHLR
4	Be capable of following instructions in various formats (written, video, audio, etc.).						
	0 (0%)	4 (4.7)	9 (10.6)	25 (29.4)	47 (55.3)	4.3529	VHLR
5	Utilize additional resources to answer course-related questions (course content, assignments, etc.).						
	3 (3.5)	1 (1.2)	7 (8.2)	27 (31.8)	47 (55.3)	4.3412	VHLR
Overall						4.4094	VHLR
6	Devote hours per week regularly for the online class.						
	0 (0%)	6 (7.1)	16 (18.8)	24 (28.2)	39 (45.9)	4.1294	HLR
7	Stay on task and avoid distractions while studying.						
	3 (3.5)	3 (3.5)	15 (17.6)	21 (24.7)	43 (50.6)	4.1529	HLR
8	Utilize course schedule for due dates.						
	0 (0%)	3 (3.5)	15 (17.6)	25 (29.4)	42 (49.4)	4.2471	VHLR
9	Complete course activities/assignments on time.						
	2	0	19	15	49	4.2824	VHLR

	(2.4)	(0%)	(22.4)	(17.6)	(57.6)		
10	Meeting multiple deadlines for course activities						
	1 (1.2)	0 (0%)	20 (23.5)	26 (30.6)	38 (44.7)	4.1765	HLR
Overall						4.1976	HLR
11	Use asynchronous technologies (discussion boards, email, etc.).						
	0 (0%)	1 (1.2)	14 (16.5)	36 (42.4)	34 (40)	4.2118	VHLR
12	Use synchronous technologies (Webex, Collaborate, Adobe Connect, Zoom, etc.) to communicate.						
	0 (0%)	6 (7.1)	11 (12.9)	28 (32.9)	40 (47.1)	4.2000	VHLR
13	Ask the instructor for help via email, discussion board, or chat.						
	0 (0%)	3 (3.5)	19 (22.4)	18 (21.2)	45 (52.9)	4.2353	VHLR
14	Ask classmates for support (accessing the course, clarification on a topic).						
	1 (1.2)	1 (1.2)	16 (18.8)	22 (25.9)	45 (52.9)	4.2824	VHLR
15	Discuss feedback received (assignments, quizzes, discussion, etc.) with the instructor.						
	3 (3.5)	2 (2.4)	11 (12.9)	28 (32.9)	41 (48.2)	4.2000	VHLR
Overall						4.2259	VHLR
16	Complete basic computer operations (e.g., creating and editing documents, managing files, and folders).						
	0 (0%)	4 (4.7)	9 (10.6)	18 (21.2)	54 (63.5)	4.4353	VHLR
17	Navigate through the course in the Learning Management System (e.g., Moodle, Canvas, Blackboard, etc.)						
	0 (0%)	3 (3.5)	12 (14.1)	35 (41.2)	35 (41.2)	4.2000	VHLR
18	Participate in course activities (discussions, quizzes, and assignments. synchronous sessions).						
	4 (4.7)	1 (1.2)	7 (8.2)	23 (27.1)	50 (58.8)	4.3412	VHLR
19	Access the online grade book for feedback on performance.						
	0 (0%)	3 (3.5)	20 (23.5)	31 (36.5)	31 (36.5)	4.0588	HLR
20	Access online help desk/tech support for assistance.						
	0 (0%)	2 (2.4)	13 (15.3)	35 (41.2)	35 (41.2)	4.2494	VHLR
Overall						4.2494	VHLR

The descriptive data of the three components revealed in Table 2.0 was interpreted to have a Very High Level of Readiness except the time management which only had a high level of readiness. Majority of the items in the four competencies rated to have a mean value higher than 4.0. Furthermore, the four competencies showed to have a High readiness level indicating that these competencies are important for Culture and Arts Students' online learning.

The interpretation of the data revealed that item number 3, "Learn from a variety of formats" was perceived by the culture and Arts students as Very Important which is interpreted to Very High Level of Readiness. This only means that the students give importance on the different online platforms that they could possibly use to achieve online learning. Since internet has been a huge factor in providing academic and non academic learning sources, the students are now relying on different online platforms to learn. Furthermore, online class platforms such as Google meet and Microsoft Teams are the medium of learning these days, making the students perceived these online formats as Very important. This coincides with Gregorio (2022) that the use of the web as a teaching tool can boost students' satisfaction as well as their learning interest which is vital in their learning process.

Further interpretation of the data found out that the Culture and Arts students gave high importance on their online attributes for their ability to learn from a variety of formats and their personal goals in setting deadlines which has a mean score of 4.4094 interpreted as High Level of Readiness. However, most of the literatures perceived technical competence to have a high importance .

5. CONCLUSION

The findings of this study revealed that there is a very high level of readiness in online learning in terms of importance and high level of readiness in terms of confidence among Culture and Arts students. This suggests that despite the sudden shift of the learning platform, students are still ready to learn through the utilization of the internet and digital tools. Learners' communication with their peers greatly helped in boosting their confidence in online learning. Moreover, learning online and accessing diverse web-based learning tools are found to be very important for the knowledge acquisition of the students in this major.

The study unveiled that with a preponderance of the respondents, time management received the least mean score. Albeit it garnered the lowest average score, the figures translate that participant show a high level of readiness toward virtual learning. Participants place an emphasis on the various online platforms that they utilize to conduct online learning. Students are now dependent on many online platforms to study since the internet has become a big element in delivering academic and non-academic learning materials. Further data analysis revealed that Culture and Arts students placed a high value on their online characteristics for their capacity to engage from a wide range of formats and their own objectives in establishing deadlines, resulting in a High Level of Readiness.

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